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of Basel**

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Water content at permanent wilting point:

**An approach for rewetting air-dried soils, considering
the effect of hysteresis**

Bachelor Thesis

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Abstract

Estimating plant-available water in soil at permanent wilting point is challenging. To advance the current state of knowledge, measurements traditionally taken with the pressure plate apparatus can be compared to new data obtained using modern dewpoint hygrometer techniques. Comparing the measurements acquired with the two methods requires rewetting of air-dried soil samples, which is however complicated by the lack of a standardised method that takes into account the hysteresis effect. This thesis addresses this lack by developing, testing, and evaluating four different rewetting methods. Using the WP4-T apparatus by Decagon Device (now Meter Group), ten soil samples covering a wide range of textures were examined. The data were analysed through a two-way ANOVA considering soil properties such as clay, silt, and sand content, soil organic compound, bulk density, and management practices (fertiliser application and tillage method) and the rewetting method. The results reveal that only one method was successful in rewetting more than a single sample. Soil properties played a significant role for the effectiveness of rewetting: Soils with high silt content (>40%) achieved the best results, while sandy soils (>50% sand content) and soils from no tillage sites performed poorly. Further research should implement a novel rewetting method, considering the increased hysteresis effect caused by the presence of water-repellent compounds.

Keywords: permanent wilting point, rewetting, hysteresis, soil properties, WP4 apparatus

1 Introduction

The concept of plant-available water in soil, defined as the difference in the water content of the soil between field capacity ($pF = 1.8$) and the permanent wilting point (PWP) ($pF = 4.2$), is fundamental for understanding soil moisture dynamics and plant growth [2, p. 228]. However, measurement discrepancies resulting from the use of different instruments, particularly the classical pressure plate apparatus (PPA) and modern dewpoint hygrometer techniques, such as those conducted with the WP4 apparatus (by Meter Group formerly Decagon Device), hinder accurately determining plant-available water (see Tuller and Or, 2023 for a description of these methods). Research has shown that the PPA tends to yield higher water content values at the permanent wilting point compared to the WP4 apparatus, which results in lower estimates of plant-available water [3]. Despite this well-documented discrepancy, there is a lack of studies that systematically examine these measurement differences and analyse how they relate to soil properties.

In principle, such a systematic comparison of paired PPA and WP4 measurements from existing and newly collected data is feasible. For the comparison, the soil samples previously analysed with the PPA need to be re-measured with the WP4 apparatus, which requires rewetting. This is methodologically challenging as there exists no standardised rewetting method that accounts for the effects of hysteresis, that is, the effects of drying and wetting on a soil's water content at a given matric potential [4].

To address this lack of a standardised rewetting method, this thesis draws on existing research by Kirste et al. (2019), Torres et al. (2021), and Schelle et al. (2013) and develops a rewetting method that aims to minimise the hysteresis effect at PWP. The ten soil samples, covering a wide range of soil textures, originate from SoilX and the soil mapping project in Bleienbach, located in the Canton of Bern (Figure 1) [5], [6], [7], [8]. Building on one another, four different rewetting methods (Treatments) were designed (RW1-RW4) and applied to the soil samples. They differ in terms of the amount and the way the water is added to the soil and the equilibration time. The data obtained by the WP4 apparatus is analysed by means of a two-way ANOVA.

Figure 1: The soil texture triangle shows the ten samples used in this thesis. P24A, ZOFFE, and FAST are samples from SoilX. Bleienbach 4, 5, and 9 are samples from a soil mapping project in the Canton of Bern.

The results show that the success of rewetting depends on the method applied as well as on the soil properties. Only one method (RW4), in which degassed water was used, was able to rewet more than just one soil successfully. Even though the methods achieved rewetting of soils with high silt content ($>40\%$), they were unable to rewet sandy soils ($>50\%$ sand content). The analysis further revealed that agricultural practices are likely to have a greater influence on the success of rewetting, as no tillage sites tend to have higher hydrophobicity, which enhances hysteresis [9, 10]. In sum, the findings of this thesis demonstrate the importance of accounting for the effects of hysteresis and soil properties in rewetting air-dried samples and emphasise the need for future research to use a novel rewetting method.

In this thesis, ChatGPT (OpenAI) was used for textual improvements as well as for the enhancement and support of coding [11].

1.1 Water Content

Knowing the water content in a soil sample is necessary to determine chemical and physical properties, such as soil water conductivity and retention. Water content can be specified gravimetrically or volumetrically. In this thesis, the gravimetric water (GWC) content is used, as it was analytically determined and due to a lack of knowledge of the bulk density for certain samples. Water content is defined as:

$$\theta_m = \frac{m_{gm} - m_{gd}}{m_{gd} - m_c} \quad (1)$$

where θ_m is the gravimetric water content [$g_{water} g_{soil}^{-1}$], m_{gm} the gross mass of the moist sample [g], and m_{gd} the gross mass of the dry sample [g]. Since the soil is filled into a plastic cup, also the cup's weight m_c [g] must be considered in the equation. This will be further discussed in Section 3 [12], [13], [14, Chapter 5].

To measure water content a direct method is used, which measures change in mass after oven drying. Direct methods require the water to be removed from the sample. Whereby the change in mass is determined by weighting the moist sample and drying and reweighting it. It is common for this procedure to use an oven operating at 105°C for at least 48 hours. Previous measurements

indicate that the plastic cups also lose weight during the process of drying. Although the amount of loss is small, it will be considered in the analysis (Eq. 6) [12], [13].

1.2 Water Potential

The total water potential describes the amount of work needed to transport a unit of water (volume, mass, or weight) from one point to another point. It is defined as the sum of the gravitational, matric, pneumatic, osmotic, and gas potential. The dew point technique measures the osmotic and matric potential. However, the osmotic component is neglected, based on the assumption, that the samples do not contain salts. However, to address the water availability for plants, the term water potential is used. In most cases it is defined as the sum of the gravitational and matric potential. The water potential Ψ [MPa] is inherently negative since it measures the difference between unsaturated samples and the atmosphere [14, Chapter 6.4], [2, Chapter 6.4.2].

1.2.1 Water Potential Measurement with WP4-T

The water potential measurements are conducted using the WP4-T dew point measurement device from the Meter Group (used to be Decagon Device, Inc.) (Figure 2a and b). This device measures the sum of matric and osmotic potentials of a sample utilizing the chilled-mirror dew point technique. It determines the vapor pressure p by measuring the condensation on the mirror within the device. When the air in the WP4 chamber is in equilibrium with the sample, the following relationship can be established for the matric potential,

$$\Psi = \frac{RT}{M} \cdot \ln \frac{p}{p_0} \quad (2)$$

where R is the gas constant, T the temperature in Kelvin, M the molecular mass of water, p the vapor pressure of the air, and p_0 the saturation vapor pressure. The saturation vapor pressure is calculated based on the sample temperature measured with a thermopile [15].

Figure 2: The WP4-T device used for measurements. The Samples are placed into the measurement chamber.

Since temperature influences measurements of water potential, the device is placed in a climate-controlled room to ensure constant temperature and humidity. Additionally, the temperature equilibration time is configured in such a way that the measurements only begin when the temperature of the sample and chamber differ by less than 0.5°C. The set point temperature was set to 23°C.

To ensure accuracy of results, the device is calibrated once a week using a KCl standard as provided by the manufacturer. If results deviate from the accepted range, the chamber is cleaned and the device recalibrated. The accepted range for calibration is ± 0.1 MPa of the target value of 2.21 MPa. This value is determined by interpolating two set points, $pF = -2.18$ at 20°C and $pF = -2.22$ at 25°C , which are provided by the Meter Group [15].

1.3 Soil-Water Retention Curve

The soil-water retention curve (SWRC) (Fig. 3) describes the relationship between gravimetric water content and water potential. It expresses the ability of soil to retain water. As the soils were collected in humid regions where the precipitation is greater than the evaporation, it can be assumed that salts are washed downward in the soil profile [15], [3].

Figure 3: SWR curve showing GWC depending on pF [1].

The main drying curve describes the maximum water content at a given potential, while the main wetting curve represents the minimum water content at the same potential. The matric potential of a soil lies between the two main curves and tends to follow the scanning curve, depending on whether the soil is drying or wetting. The scanning curve describes the path of the retention curve, which is taken while drying or wetting. There is an infinite amount of scanning curves, which have to be considered in the measurements [14, Chapter 7.2]. As the soil begins to dry from the saturated point θ_s , matric potential decreases. While rewetting, air can be trapped, thereby lowering the maximum water content to θ_u [1].

The SWRC exhibits hysteresis that occurs due to differences in water adsorption and water desorption. While drying, the water content is higher at a given water potential than while wetting [1]. These differences are expected to occur because of three main causes. It is assumed that the first two causes, known as Ink-bottle and Hydrophobicity, have the greatest influence on hysteresis behaviour [4], [14, Chapter 7.2].

1. Ink-Bottle Effect

The Ink-bottle effect is caused by differences in shapes of the pore spaces. During drying or rewetting, menisci appear in different places even though they have the same curvature. This leads to different saturations of the wetting fluid, while the capillary pressure is the same [4].

2. Hydrophobicity

Hydrophobicity is another behaviour that occurs while drying and rewetting. Mineral surfaces are mostly hydrophilic and thus able to interact with water molecules. Organic matter (OM) can be hydrophilic as well as hydrophobic and amphiphilic. Whereas low-molecular-weight organic acids and monomeric carbohydrates behave hydrophilic, plant residues such as lignin behave hydrophobic. The way hydrophobic soils behave after drying depends on clay content, temperature, pH, ionic strength, thickness of water layer, and on how often the drying and rewetting process was repeated. However, the main reason for the shift from hydrophilic to hydrophobic behaviour lies in amphiphilic OM. While still wet, hydrophobic compounds are covered by amphiphilic compounds, enabling the soil to be hydrophilic and thus taking up water. Drying causes the amphiphilic compounds to change their orientation so that the hydrophobic pole points outwards, which gives the soil a hydrophobic character. While rewetting, the behaviour of OM can reverse after hours/days, giving the particle surface a hydrophilic character again [9].

3. Snap-off Effect

The snap-off effect, also called cut-off effect [16], is caused by entrapped, non-wetting fluid in the pore space. It occurs during re-wetting and when the pore space diameter differs from the pore opening diameter [4].

Apart from hysteresis effects, there exist further soil behaviour while rewetting that have to be considered. One behaviour occurs during drying when soil particle surfaces are forced together. The strength of adhesion between the particles depends on precipitation and the deposition of dissolved minerals. Deposited minerals are surrounding the contact points of the particles' surfaces, thus increasing adhesion. While rewetting, entrapped air keeps the aggregates intact until capillary forces pull water inwards. Consequently, the aggregates fall apart and thereby release air. One way to foster the aggregates to disband is by applying additional mechanical dispersive forces [9].

Determining the SWRC is very labour-intensive, as there is no measurement method covering the whole matric water potential range [17, Chapter 69.4.3]. In this thesis, only the gravimetric water content at permanent wilting point is examined. It is assumed at $pF = 4.2$ (-1.55MPa). To determine the PWP, two measurement techniques, the evaporation and the dew point method, are usually used [18]. Measuring near PWP with the forced drainage method through the PPA is known for causing errors, because samples within the PPA cannot reach equilibrium [3]. Therefore, dew point devices are used in this thesis as they follow a different approach, in which the vapor pressure at equilibrium can be measured.

To reproduce the SWRC at PWP and therefore enable comparisons, all measurements should be conducted on one of the main curves, preferably the main drying curve [14, Chapter 7.2]. Aligning the GWC with the main drying curve requires a rewetting method mitigating the hysteresis effect.

1.4 Rewetting

Prior research on rewetting is sparse and differs in the methods applied. Five approaches will be further examined, taking their differences into account (Table 1). The presented methods give insight in how the rewetting process can be conducted, which informs the approach of this thesis. Kirste et al. 2019 use different methods for measuring PWP in dried soils. Two methods are of greater interest, as their samples show similarities with the samples used in this thesis. In the first method, the authors added tap water to compressed soil within stainless steel cylinders to saturate the sample. Tensiometers at different depth were added and the samples were

Table 1: *Different approaches for rewetting soil samples. All samples used for measurements were disturbed.*

Authors	Temperature dried	Rewetting methods	Equilibrium time
Kirste et al. 2019 [18]	Air-dried	(1) Soaking and (2) adding water 10% above estimated PWP	≥ 16 h
Torres et al. 2021 [16]	Air-dried	Humidifier	≥ 48 h
Schelle et al. 2013 [19]	Oven-dried (105°C)	Add estimated water for PWP	Not mentioned
Haney et al. 2010 [20]	Oven-dried (50°C)	Soil:Water ratio 40g:30ml	No equilibration
Kjaergaard et al. 2004 [21]	Air-dried	Soil:Water ratio 1:8 (g soil/g water) and shaken for 16 h	Wetting time 7 d. After water removal equilibrating 14 d

air dried until the lower tensiometer reached air-entry pressure. A first measurement was conducted. Thereafter, the core was cut into four slabs (1.25 cm each), which were then brayed and put into sealed containers to reach equilibrium after a few hours. Thereafter, the samples were measured with a WPC4 apparatus. They contrasted this first approach with a method relying on air-dried soil. Before rewetting, the amount of water to be added was calculated based on measurements from the oven-dried samples. The authors added a safety margin of 10% to the calculated amount. In a next step, the samples were mixed and the containers sealed for at least 16 hours to let the sample reach equilibrium before taking the measurements.

The approach by Torres et al. 2021 differs in the method used for rewetting. In a first step, the authors used undisturbed samples, with a subsamples being put in a humidified chamber. In a second step, they took out the subsamples at different times, mixed them with tap water, and sealed the containers for 48 hours to equilibrate. After the equilibration, the authors measured the samples with a WP4-T apparatus

Schelle et al. 2013 state that the measured range of the dew point method is “almost exclusively texture based ” [19, p. 815]. They therefore used disturbed samples.

The method applied by Kjaergaard et al. 2024 was not used for measuring water content at dew point, but to measure low-energy water-dispersible colloids as a function of initial matric potential at -1.5 MPa. As the aim of rewetting is the same, the method could be applied to water-content measurements. After mixing soil with water in a ratio 1:8 (w/w), the samples were shaken for 16 h. After gravitational sedimentation, water was removed and the samples dried and in a next step let to be wet for 7 d. Lastly, the samples were dried by the atmosphere and afterwards sealed for 14 d to equilibrate within sealed containers.

2 Method Laboratory

The following chapters describe the empirical approach of this thesis. Firstly, data which consists of pre-existing data and new measured data will be introduced. Data is stored in an Excel-file to be used in the open-source statistical software R [22]. Secondly, the methods carried out in the laboratory are outlined.

2.1 Sample Selection

For the analysis, ten samples from two different projects were chosen to cover a broad range of the soil texture triangle. The samples originate from SoilX and the soil mapping project in Bleienbach, located in the Canton of Bern. SoilX is a research project that investigates potential mitigation measures through improved soil management practices in response to the effects of extreme weather events such as drought and heavy precipitation [5].

Firstly, SoilX samples consist of measurements from three different long-term experiments conducted across Switzerland, whereas each experiment involves different management practices. A total of seven samples were selected from the initial collection based on their texture. Secondly, three samples from a soil mapping project carried out by the municipality of Bleienbach BE (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Locations of the four sample sites. The Experiment of ZOFÉ and FAST are conducted at the same Location at Reckenholz in Affoltern ZH. P24A is placed near Nyon (Own illustration).

The Bleienbach samples were included because they differ from the SoilX samples regarding their texture and thereby expand the range of the data (Table 2). While the Bleienbach samples do not include data on SOC, they contain information on the organic matter content in percentage. Using a reference method from Agroscope, the organic compound was converted into SOM by a conversion factor of 1.725 (Eq. 3) [23].

$$\text{SOM}[\%] = 1.725 \cdot \text{TOC}[\%] \quad (3)$$

Olivier Heller measured the fresh samples with the WP4-T apparatus. The unused soil samples were dried at 40°C. Afterward, the samples were put into storage. The SoilX samples were stored in a dry storage room at room temperature. To examine the rewetting procedure, these samples were selected to allow a comprehensive comparison.

While SoilX data already included information on the fresh samples, the Bleienbach samples, were still stored fresh in a fridge at 4°C. Therefore, they had to be measured and dried at 40°C before conducting the rewetting procedure.

Table 2: Chosen samples for the analysis. ID 1-7 are SoilX samples, 8-10 are samples from Bleienbach. Samples from Bleienbach are not from experimental sites and therefore, there is no information available on management practice and on block. Block is referring to the experimental repetition within each long-term field experiment (usually A-D).

ID	Experiment	Management Practice	Block	Description	Coordinates	Depth [cm]	BD [g/cm ³]	SOC [%]	Clay [%]	Silt [%]	Sand [%]	Source
1	P24A	MIN	B	Inversion tillage, Minimal fertilisation	46°23'55"N, 06°14'24"E	7.5 - 12.5	1.47	0.9	10.96	41.12	47.92	[24, 25]
2	P24A	FYM	D	Inversion tillage	46°23'55"N, 06°14'24"E	7.5 - 12.5	1.45	1.13	22.53	44.95	32.52	[24, 25]
3	ZOFE	COM	B	Inversion tillage, Combined mineral and organic fertilisation	47°25'37"N, 08°31'06"E	7.5 - 12.5	1.54	1.07	11.61	29.74	58.66	[26]
4	ZOFE	MIN	C	Inversion tillage, Minimal fertilisation	47°25'37"N, 08°31'06"E	7.5 - 12.5	1.57	0.73	14.89	24.92	60.18	[26]
5	FAST	CNT	A	Conventional no tillage, mineral fertilisation	47°26'N, 08°31'E	27.5 - 32.5	1.52	0.68	19.13	23.79	57.09	[27]
6	FAST	CNT	D	Conventional no tillage, mineral fertilisation	47°26'N, 08°31'E	27.5 - 32.5	1.43	0.7	27.23	36.03	36.74	[27]
7	FAST	CIT	B	Conventional intensive tillage, mineral fertilisation	47°26'N, 08°31'E	7.5 - 12.5	1.31	1.47	22.05	37.33	40.62	[27]
8	Bleienbach_4	-	-	Ah,p-ABw,g-Bw,g(g)-(B)Cgg-ICr-IICr Sample horizon unknown	47°10'01"N, 07°42'50"E	-	1.86 (SOM)	51	31	18	-	[6]
9	Bleienbach_5	-	-	Ah,p-[A]Bw,g-Bw,gg-CBw,gg-Cgg,r-Cr Sample horizon unknown	47°10'12"N, 07°42'19"E	-	1.62 (SOM)	34	31	36	-	[7]
10	Bleienbach_9	-	-	Ah,p-Cag-[A]Cg-Cg, Sample horizon [A]Cg	47°10'48"N, 07°44'25"E	-	0.12 (SOM)	6	6	89	-	[8]

2.2 Soil Sample Preparation

After selecting the samples, the next step was to prepare them for the analysis. Since the SoilX samples were stored in containers, the soil was not homogenous and therefore not fully representative. To ensure homogeneity, each soil was mixed using the 3D shake mixer Turbula® from Willy A. Bachofen AG. Each soil was mixed for ten minutes and subsequently within one minute the required amount of sample, in this case nine gram has to be taken out of the container to prevent sorting by gravity. Then, the sample is directly distributed into three plastic cups, whereby each contained three gram of soil each (Figure 5). Before the soil was added, each plastic cup was labelled with the samples ID and a specific letter A, B, or C to indicate the subsample, so that in conclusion each sample had three replicates. Additionally, each plastic cup was weighted before the soil was added to be able to subtract its weight when calculating the gravimetric and volumetric water content. The calculations will be further discussed in Section 3.1.

Figure 5: *Soil samples within plastic cups after turbulation. Each cup was filled with 3 gram of soil.*

The process for the Bleienbach samples differed from that of the SoilX samples as they were stored undried in a refrigerator by 4°C. To ensure comparable conditions, the Bleienbach samples were first sieved (2mm) and measured using the WP4-T apparatus at PWP, as described in Section 1.2.1. Afterward, the measured samples were dried in an oven at 40°C. In a next step, the samples were rewetted in order to measure their pF-value around PWP. Additionally, the GWC was determined, providing insights in the rewetting procedure.

2.3 Rewetting Measurement Procedure

The presented methods in Section 1.4 provided an overview of how the rewetting process can be conducted. Consequently, four different approaches (Treatments) were developed and named RW1, RW2, RW3 and RW4. The following sections will describe the four rewetting procedures in more detail. Given that the SoilX samples had already been measured, the methods from the rewetting procedures 1, 2, and 4 were designed so as to minimise potential errors, which can occur through variation in the sample preparations.

One significant factor assumed to influence the measurements is whether the sample is in equilibrium within itself and with the surrounding atmosphere or not. A potential discrepancy is expected to be caused by the lid on the plastic cup. With the lid in place, the sample can

reach equilibrium after a certain period. According to Kjaergaard et al. 2004 and Kirste et al. 2019, soil samples are expected to reach equilibrium after ≥ 16 hours. Measurements in equilibrium state were only conducted with RW3. After each WP4 measurement, the subsample was weighted so as to calculate the gravimetric and volumetric water content using R [21], [18].

2.3.1 Rewetting procedure 1 (RW1)

The first procedure aims at a water potential just below the wilting point, similarly to the approach by Kirste et al. [18] and Schelle et al. [19]. The primary goal is to minimise drying time and to facilitate effective reproducibility. To reach this point, a regression analysis was conducted, using clay as the predictor variable given its high specific surface area that can adsorb water [2, Chapter 5.5]. For each plot and depth, the average GWC at pF 4.2 for all SoilX samples was calculated to develop the regression model based on clay content, resulting in a factor of 0.0053. In addition to the linear regression model, the sample mass of 3g and a safety margin of 50% on top of the calculated amount of water were multiplied (Eq. 4).

$$\text{water to add [g]} = \text{clay [\%]} \cdot 0.0053 \cdot \text{sample mass [g]} \cdot 1.5 \quad (4)$$

After preparing the sample as described in Section 2.2, water was evenly distributed onto the sample using a syringe. To ensure equilibration, the plastic cup were closed with a lid for at least one week. The lid prevents evaporation during this period. Afterward, the samples were carefully mixed with a needle and subsequently measured in the WP4-T apparatus. Following the first measurement, each sub sample was dried for an indeterminate period (few minutes). Afterwards, they were measured again, tracking the drying curve of the hysteresis. A total of three measurements for each replicate were taken to ensure valid data. During the drying phase, the lid was removed from the plastic cup and the samples was no longer in equilibrium with the gaseous phase at the time of the measurement, resulting in a higher water content for a certain pF value.

2.3.2 Rewetting procedure 2 (RW2)

Based on findings from RW1 discussed later, RW2 was developed. As done by Kaiser et al. 2015 and Kirste et al. 2019, this method uses a larger water-to-soil ratio [g/g] for rewetting, aiming for a high GWC at high matric potential [9], [18]. This increases the likelihood of the samples to follow the main drying curve while drying to the wilting point. Therefore, RW2 is expected to have a higher GWC at PWP compared to RW1. Since the amount of added water to 3g of soil stored in the plastic cups varies depending on the samples' texture, water was added until a viscous soil behaviour was observed while mixing with a needle.

As done in RW1 the plastic cups were sealed for one week to ensure equilibration. After one week the plastic cups were opened to allow water evaporate until a water potential lower than -1.0 MPa is reached. Prior to each measurement, the samples were stirred with a needle. Since the upper and the lower part of the sample differs in water content. Stirring mixes the dry surface with the wetter interior, expected to result in a more homogenic moistened sample and hence more accurate measurements. As in RW1, three points along the drying curve were measured. Between each measurement the sample was dried by air for a few minutes so as to increase the water potential within the soil.

2.3.3 Rewetting procedure 3 (RW3)

The method of RW3 is based on RW2 using 3g of soil per subsample. However, the method differs in two key aspects. Firstly, based on findings of RW2, the samples were no longer stirred before taking the measurement. Secondly, the plastic cups were sealed with a lid and Parafilm

for at least 16 hours to allow the sample reach equilibrium. The tape guaranties that exchange with the outer atmosphere is minimised. Once the soil reaches equilibrium, the measurements are expected to show a lower GWC at the same matric potential compared to the imbalanced state. While the sample equilibrates, the total water content remains unchanged due to the sealed plastic cup, which results in a decreased water potential. This method aims to give insight for further comparison with PPA. Since the sample need time to equilibrate – and based on results from RW1 and RW2, which show that the measurement points are very close to each other – only one measurement per subsample was taken. The three replicates were dried with different durations to achieve distinct measurement points along the drying curve.

2.3.4 Rewetting procedure 4 (RW4)

RW4 was developed based on the results from RW2. This new approach includes additional steps to increase the GWC. One problem the rewetting methods faces is the built-up of compressed air within the soil pores while capillary forces draw water into them [9]. To diminish this effect, degassed water was used, as the water is not in equilibrium with the gaseous phase and is expected to dissolve some of the entrapped compressed air. The degassed water was produced by boiling MilliQ water for 20-30 minutes in a 100 ml Erlenmeyer from Pyrex on a stove. Using a 1:1 water-to-soil ratio, 3 ml of degassed water was added to 3 g of soil. Additionally, the samples were placed in a vacuum chamber at 50 mbar for one hour to boil up the water to keep the water degassed until it was taken up by the soil. As done in procedure RW2 the samples were put aside to equilibrate and dry.

2.4 Sample Drying

After completing the measurements, the samples were dried in the oven (Figure 6a). This process eliminates all water bounded in soil. Furthermore, knowing the dry mass additionally to the wet mass of the sample, enables to calculate the GWC. Following the drying period, the samples were removed from the oven and placed in a sealed chamber (Figure 6b) to let them cool down while minimising water absorption from the atmosphere. The chamber contains crystals that absorb water more quickly than soil, ensuring a low humidity atmosphere inside the chamber.

(a) Oven

(b) Drying Chamber

Figure 6: *The oven is used for air-drying samples at 40°C as well to oven dry them at 105°C. For cooling down, the samples were put into the drying chamber in order to prevent water uptake.*

The samples then were weighted again. It is important to minimise exposure of the soil to the atmosphere during this process. Therefore, the plastic cups were closed with the lids until weighing. Since the plastic cups lose weight during drying, the soil within was removed, and the empty cups weighted to attain the dry plastic cup weight.

3 Statistical Evaluation

The Data analysis was performed using RStudio [22]. In addition, several packages were installed to facilitate data management, statistical analysis and graphical visualisations. The following packages were used: config [28], tidyverse [29], readxl [30], soiltexture [31], FSA [32], ggpubr [33], car [34], afex [35], dplyr [36], rcompanion [37], viridis [38], patchwork [39], emmeans [40], and ggmisc [41].

The foundation of the code was provided by Olivier Heller. This included a structured framework for writing the code, loading packages, data, and functions. Data was imported from two Excel-files. “test_samples.xlsx” contains the measurements of the different rewetting methods (RW1, RW2, RW3 and RW4), as well as measurements of the fresh Bleienbach samples. The file “SoilX_Data_for_PPAsWP4.xlsx” included all previous measurements of fresh samples from SoilX. These datasets were assigned to two new subsets: data_soilx_raw and data_wp4_raw. Additionally, unnecessary data was filtered out. To optimise the workflow, variables were renamed and restructured in a section labelled “Wrangle Data”.

3.1 Wrangle Data

To conduct the analysis, the subsets were converted from wide-format into long-format using the function pivot_longer(), allowing each row to represent a single observation. In case of data_soilx_raw, the GWC of each observation was already calculated. Variables were renamed, in order to align with data_wp4. The data was assigned to a new subset data_soilx.

Enabling binding the two data sets, all values were merged into the same format. Thus, the pF value for the subset data_wp4_raw was calculated from the measured potential. The potential was multiplied as it was measured in MPa (Eq. 5).

$$\text{pF} = -\log_{10}(\text{pot} \cdot 10000) \quad (5)$$

The GWC in the subset data_wp4_raw was calculated using the sample’s mass change, considering the mass of the plastic cup (Eq. 6). Thus, the following equation was derived:

$$\text{GWC} = \frac{m_{bw} - m_{bd} - (m_{tw} - m_{td})}{m_{bd} - m_{td}} \quad (6)$$

Where m_{bw} is the gross mass [g] of the wet sample, m_{bd} the gross mass [g] of the oven dried sample, m_{tw} the weight [g] of the “wet” plastic cup and m_{td} the weight [g] of the oven dried plastic cup. The gross mass is the sum of the soil (netto) and the plastic cup. Therefore, $m_{bd} - m_{td}$ calculates the netto weight of the dried sample. After renaming and regrouping variables, the updated data was assigned to a new subset data_wp4.

The two subsets, data_wp4 and data_soilx, were then merged using rbind(). The combined dataset was further processed to predict the GWC at $\text{pF} = 4.2$ for each subsample and treatment using a linear regression model.

The fitted data was assigned to data_total and refined further, selecting only the necessary data for statistical analysis, resulting in the final subset data_stat.

3.2 Statistical Analysis

To compare GWC at $pF = 4.2$, a two-way ANOVA was conducted, using ID and treatment as independent variables. Therefore following assumption were to be met [42]:

1. Normal distribution of residuals (checked visually and with the Shapiro-Wilk test using the residuals of the fitted model)
2. Equal variances within groups (tested using Levene test from the car package)
3. Independence of errors

To determine whether the effect of one independent variable (ID or treatment) on the dependent variable GWC_4.2 is influenced by the other independent variable, interaction plots were generated. Two separate plots were created: One with treatment as the trace factor and one with ID as the trace factor.

In a next step, the two-way ANOVA was performed. Due to insufficient data, an unbalanced design type III from the afex package [35] was addressed. To ensure sum of contrasts equals zero, `contrasts()` was set to `contr.sum`, providing interpretable main and interaction effects. Each variable was given an unique index, in order to meet the function's requirements of an error term. Since interpreting two-way ANOVA results can be complex, a post-hoc analysis was performed using `emmeans()` function from the `emmeans` package [40].

The Bonferroni method was applied to adjust p-values for multiple comparisons, offering a conservative approach [42]. Pairwise comparisons were performed for each treatment within each ID. Since only the comparisons between Fresh and RWx treatments were of interest, an additional filter was applied. The differences between the various rewetting methods (RWx) were not relevant, as all methods aim to achieve the fresh state.

4 Results and Discussion

This section reports on the outcome of the WP4-T measurements and presents the findings of the statistical analyses thereof. The main finding is that the outcome of the rewetting depends on the RW-Method as well as on the soil. Soil properties such as SOC and soil texture are possible key factors in determining how well rewetting works.

4.1 WP4-T Measurements

The figures below show the outcome of the four series of WP4-T measurements. As illustrated in Figure 7a, b, and d, most data points are closely clustered, indicating that the model provides an accurate prediction of the GWC at PWP for each sample. The sub-samples exhibit similar slopes. In line with the expected hysteresis pattern, the figures show that as the pF value increases, the GWC decreases. Yet, Soil 1 contains outliers as evident in Figure 7a (Subsample B), 7b (Subsample A), and 7d (Subsample C). A similar observation is made in Figure 7b for Soil 6 (Subsample A). These outliers can result from various factors such as:

- errors in weighing,
- uneven moisture distribution within the sample,
- measurement errors of the WP4 device,
- measurement uncertainties of the WP4 device near -1.0 MPa,
- incorrectly recorded values from the measuring instrument, and
- sample loss/spillage due to handling.

These outliers likely affect the normal distribution and hence potentially bias the outcome of the statistical analysis. They were still considered in the statistical analysis. However, the effect on the results must be examined closer in the analysis.

Apart from these outliers potentially biasing the outcome of the statistical analyses, a further problem is caused by the subsamples' sizes. Firstly, there exist a lack of data for Soils 8, 9, and 10 in RW2 caused by excessive drying, insufficient sample material, and spillage. Similarly, no measurements are available for these samples in RW4 given the insufficient available soil material. Thus, the values for Soils 8-10 have been excluded from the statistical analysis.

Secondly, each subsample of RW3, presented in Figure 7c, was only measured once. The adopted approach of conducting a two-factor ANOVA requires more than one measurement. While these values could be used in a multi-factor analysis, doing so would substantially complicate the evaluation. RW3 has hence been excluded from the statistical analysis.

Figure 7: Gravimetric water content around permanent wilting point for ten rewetted soils, treated with four different rewetting methods (RW1 (a)–RW4 (d)). Measurements were conducted using a WP4-T apparatus. Each subsample was measured three times at different pF values, except for subsamples in (c), which were measured only once. For Soils 8–10, limited sample availability allowed for only a few measurements.

Figures 8a, b, and c, as well as Figures 9a and b depict the measurement points based on GWC and pF. Soil properties, i.e., each sample’s relative amount of clay, silt, and sand, SOC, and its average bulk density, are highlighted by means of colour coding.

Figures 8a, b, and c visually illustrate the relationship between GWC at PWP and soil properties. They reveal a positive relationship between GWC at PWP and clay content, and a reversed relationship between GWC at PWP and sand content. This behaviour can be explained by the

specific surface area of clay and sand particles, with clay having a much larger specific surface area than sand grains [2, p. 169], [43]. It follows that more water can adhere to clay minerals in the form of a thin film. Due to their size and shape, clay minerals also have more contact points within a given volume, which facilitates water adhesion. Additionally, clay minerals have lower pore volumes, which leads to stronger water retention due to capillary forces compared to coarser Soil fractions [2, p. 283].

Figure 8: Gravimetric water content as a function of pF strongly depends on soil characteristics. Soil properties are plotted with colour coding to visualise potential effects on the variables. All three graphs show a trend.

Notably, the gradients of sand content and BD are almost identical. Intuitively, one might assume that BD decreases with increasing sand content since pure sand has a higher pore volume—unless clay particles are arranged in a "house-of-cards" structure. However, the significant amounts of silt and clay contribute to a higher BD. The smaller particles fill the pores between larger particles, thereby enabling denser packing [2, p. 229].

While the gradient for BD is visually less distinct (Figure 8a), a trend is visible: GWC at PWP decreases as BD increases. This can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, as BD increases, the Soil's water storage capacity is likely to decrease due to less pore space available to retain water. Secondly, higher density aggravates water infiltration as less water can enter the pores.

Figure 9: Based on the pF-value and the gravimetric water content; soil properties are plotted with colour coding to visualise potential effects on the variables. Both graphs show no strong trend nor pattern.

The potential influence of silt and SOC were also examined, whereby no clear trend is observable. Soils with low silt content are located in the mid-range of the GWC spectrum, whereas soils with higher silt content appear in both, the lower and upper range (Figure 9a). Regarding SOC content, soils with high SOC levels are positioned in the mid-range, whereas soils with lower SOC levels can exhibit both high and low GWC values (Figure 9b).

4.2 Testing Assumptions for Two-way ANOVA

Normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test, which is well-suited for a dataset with $n = 83$ measurements, as described in Section 3. The Shapiro-Wilk test results in ($W=0.88418$, $p\text{-value}=1.934e-06$), which means that the assumption of normal distribution is violated as illustrated in Figure 10, thereby leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Figure 10: *Distribution of residuals with ranked values. The values >0.02 [g/g] indicate stronger outlier, possibly causing the rejection of Normality.*

Although the distribution is approximately bell-shaped, significant outliers are evident. The residuals can reach values greater 0.02 [g/g]. The two residuals greater 0.02 [g/g] can be identified as Subsample A from Soils 1 and 5 from the method RW2. Since most points are symmetrically distributed and cluster around zero, it is safe to assume that most residuals are small. This suggests that the model provides good predictive performance.

The Levene test assessing homogeneity of variance results in $F(27,55)=0.68$, $p\text{-value}=0.86$. The assumption of homogeneity of variance can hence be accepted.

4.3 Interaction Plots

The figures below show the interaction between the RW-methods and the soil samples.

Figure 11: Interaction plot showing the effect of the soil sample on the rewetting method. Different gradients indicate that the soil sample has an effect on rewetting.

Figures 11a, b, and c show a predominantly negative slope (15 negative and 6 positive slopes). This indicates that GWC measurements are generally higher for Fresh samples than for the rewetted ones. Additionally, the slopes vary in the gradient, suggesting that the rewetting methods influence the GWC of the respective samples.

With the further development from RW2 to RW4, the slope decreases sharply for Soils 1 and 2. Soil 1 even exhibits a positive slope, likely due to the outliers that are particularly noticeable in RW2 and RW4 (Figure 1b and d). A smaller increase in GWC is observed for Soil 3, indicating a small effect of the rewetting method RW4 compared to RW2. For Soil 7, only a slight slope can be seen with RW4, indicating that there is almost no difference between Fresh and RW4.

For Soils 4 and 5, the GWC does not significantly increase with the rewetting method, suggesting that the method has little impact on these soils. A strong change is evident for Soil 6 in RW2, which can potentially be attributed to the outlier visible in Figure 7b. This outlier likely causes an overestimation of GWC at PWP.

Overall, samples with high GWC at PWP tend to exhibit steeper slopes. This highlights that

the RW method has varying effects and may be more effective for Soils with lower GWC at PWP than for those with higher GWC at PWP.

Figure 12: Interaction plot showing the effect of the rewetting method on the soil sample. Different gradients indicate that the rewetting method has an effect on rewetting.

Figures 12a, b, and c illustrate interactions between soil types and rewetting methods. For Soils 1, 2, 3, and 7, the gaps between the rewetting methods become smaller as the method advances from RW1 to RW4. This indicates that the rewetting methods influence the GWC at PWP differently in different soils.

In Figures 12b and c, it is evident that the line for Soil 1 is significantly above that of Fresh. For Soils 4 and 5, almost no visual change is noticeable. This strengthens the previous assumption from Figure 11 that the rewetting method has little effect on these soils. A similar trend is apparent for Soil 6. While a positive effect of the rewetting method is visible, the results in Figure 12b are likely influenced by an outlier.

It can be concluded that the rewetting method can impact water content, but that this effect depends on the soil type. At the same time, the soil itself influences the water content, which in turn depends on the method used. Visually, the RW2 and RW4 methods work well for Soils 1 and 2. RW4 works particularly well for Soil 7. While the further development of the RW1-RW4 method shows an improvement of Soil 3. All methods are noticeably below the level of Fresh. For Soils 4 and 5, hardly any effect is evident. Soil 6 will be closer discussed in Section 4.5, as its outlier could distort the picture.

4.4 Two-Way ANOVA

Despite the violation of normality, a two-way ANOVA was conducted. It was assumed that the results remain robust due to the large sample size. For further validation of the results, GWC values at PWP were ranked and an ANOVA was conducted based on these data. This approach minimises the impact of potential large outliers on the results, thereby mitigating the effect of the violated normality assumption.

Table 3: Results of the unmodified two-way ANOVA. RW rewetting method, DF degrees of freedom, SS sum of squares. The effects and their interaction indicate high significance.

Effect	DF	SS	F-Value	p -Value	
(Intercept)	1	0.65031	6860.9490	< 2.2e-16	***
Soil	6	0.04486	78.8846	< 2.2e-16	***
RW	3	0.00678	23.8335	5.155e-10	***
Soil:RW	18	0.00502	2.9407	0.001096	**
Residuals	55	0.00521			

Table 4: Results of the ranked model two-way ANOVA. RW rewetting method. DF degrees of freedom, SS sum of squares The effects and their interaction indicate high significance.

Effect	DF	SS	F-Value	p -Value	
(Intercept)	1	146941	2396.8477	< 2.2e-16	***
Soil	6	34179	92.9197	< 2.2e-16	***
RW	3	5985	32.5394	3.133e-12	***
Soil:RW	18	2814	2.5503	0.004044	**
Residuals	55	3372			

Results from both models indicate that all three effects are statistically significant, which underscores the robustness of the analysis (Table 3 and 4). The sum of squares (SS) of Soil are in both models higher than the ones from RWx, indicating that the soil has a higher impact on the success of rewetting than the rewetting method. The SS of the interaction is smaller in both cases, suggesting that the interaction explains additional variance beyond the main effects.

The SS of the main effects are marginally higher in the rank model, whereas the interaction effects are slightly lower. These differences likely occur because of the outliers' reduced influence in the rank model. The F-value, reflecting the effect sizes in both analyses, is also higher in the rank model. Consequently, both models indicate robustness of the analysis despite the violation of normality.

The effects' high significance suggests that structurally similar results can be expected regardless of whether the rank model is used or not. It also confirms existing differences between the various samples. Both models show that the GWC at PWP is strongly affected by the soil as well as the rewetting method. The significant interaction effect indicates that the method also influences the soil and vice-versa. The relatively small residuals suggest that the model captures most of the variance in GWC at PWP.

4.5 Outliers

Throughout the conducted analyses, Subsample A of Soils 1 and 6 in the RW2 method were identified as outliers. Removing them leads to improvement of normality and the hypothesis can hence be accepted ($W = 0.97543$, $p\text{-value} = 0.1213$). The homogeneity of variance remains intact. After removing the outliers, the interaction plot shows a negative slope for Soil 6 in RW2 (see comparison with Figure 11b), indicating a decrease in GWC compared to Fresh. Removing the outliers had only a negligible effect on the ANOVA results. They will be neglected for the post-hoc analysis to enable better comparison.

4.6 Post-hoc Analysis

The post-hoc analysis (Figure 13) illustrates the impact of each RW method on the measured GWC at PWP for the Soils 1-7. It is evident that Soils 1 and 2 respond well to the rewetting methods, as does Soil 7 with RW4 to some extent. Although Soil 6 with RW2 is initially insignificant, removing the outlier resulted in significant differences arising from the treatment.

It is further noticeable that RW4 improves GWC in multiple soils, while for Soils 4 and 5 only a slight improvement is observed. It requires further investigation to determine why no clear effect is apparent. Soil 3 using the RW2 method was classified as insignificant. However, visually, no effect is noticeable. This means that the soil's insignificance could be caused by the wide data spread. The low variance across the different methods indicates a robust data basis, further strengthening the validity of the analysis.

Figure 13: Conducted post-hoc analysis with the rewetting methods and Soils 1-7, with the mean gravimetric water content at permanent wilting point as dependent variable. The treatments are ranked based on their statistical significance, ranging from strongly significant to insignificant. Insignificant values indicate that the rewetting procedure is likely effective. The scales of the y-axes vary in order to guarantee legibility.

The rewetting methods for Soils 1, 2, and 7 result in a noticeable increase in GWC. With RW4, the GWC of Fresh could be successfully reproduced. In contrast, Soils 3, 4, 5, and 6 exhibit differences greater than 0.01 [g/g], indicating that the rewetting process was less effective in these soils.

4.7 Relative Difference

From the post-hoc analysis, the relative difference of the median can be derived. Expressing the medians in relative values provides a clearer understanding of the methods' effectiveness (Table 5).

For Soil 1, RW2 performs slightly better than RW4, but the higher variance in the data may indicate distortion. For Soil 2, both methods are highly effective, with RW2 and RW4 achieving differences below 5%. However, there exists a relatively high variance. Soil 7 with RW4 also achieves a relative difference of <5%. Soils 4, 5, and 6 respond poorly to the methods, with RW4 even worsening the effect. For Soil 6, RW2 initially improves GWC at PWP, but RW4 causes a significant deterioration of 7.6%. Soil 3 improves with applying the more advanced methods, but the difference for RW4 from Fresh exceeds 10%.

Table 5: *Relative difference of the median of the rewetting method from Fresh [%] with the absolute mean value [%] of each soil and each rewetting method. The three identified outliers were omitted from this analysis. RW rewetting method (1-4), Abs. Mean absolute mean.*

ID	RW1	RW2	RW4	Abs. Mean
Soil 1	-26.1	-10.5	8.02	14.9
Soil 2	-15.4	3.9	0.139	6.5
Soil 3	-25.7	-22.2	-10.4	19.4
Soil 4	-25.3	-17.1	-19.4	20.6
Soil 5	-42.7	-24.8	-31.7	33.1
Soil 6	-31.7	-11.9	-19.5	21.0
Soil 7	-16.2	-11.1	-4.21	10.5
Abs. Mean	26.2	14.5	13.3	

From RW1 to RW4, the absolute mean nearly halved, with a slight improvement from RW2 to RW4. This implies that the RW4 method is better suited for rewetting. Soils 2 and 7 stand out due to their low absolute mean values, likely because RW1 already had a relatively strong effect on them. Soils 4, 5, and 6 remain close to the high absolute mean value with RW4. This indicates that the rewetting methods do not work well for these soils.

When examining the relationship between the relative difference from the median and soil properties (Figure 14 and Table 2) positive and negative trends emerge, notably for SOC, sand, and silt (Figure 14 b, d, and e). However, the R^2 and p-values indicate that the independent variable minimally impacts the relative difference in most instances.

Figure 14: Behaviour of the relative difference in GWC as a function of soil properties.

Comparing Figure 14a with Figure 14d underlines the co-dependency of sand content and BD, as they show a similar behaviour. Soils 3, 4, and 5 are the only soils with a sand content $>50\%$, which is reflected in their high BD. Even though soil depth has an influence on BD, no trend is apparent in the properties of the sampled soils (Table 2) and the effects on rewetting can be attributed to soil texture. It is likely that BD as a measurable soil property has no influence on the outcome of the rewetting method. In fact, the sand content has a greater influence on rewetting, as it affects BD and because of its hydrophobic characteristics. These are more pronounced compared to clayey or silty soils [44]. This implies that soils with a sand content greater 50% are less likely to succeed in rewetting.

The relative difference decreases with increasing silt content (Figure 14e). On the one hand, this could be explained by the sand content decreasing as the silt content increases. On the other hand, it could also indicate that silt is more likely to rewet due to its physical properties, such as higher capillary forces [45]. The high silt content could mean that wetting inhibition is lower than in sandy soils [2, p. 244]. This assumption is supported by the soil properties presented in Table 2, which show that soils 3-5 exhibit the highest sand content while also having the lowest silt content.

A notable observation is that Soils 1, 2, and 7 with good rewetting ability have in comparison high silt contents. The exception is Soil 6, which also has a high silt content but does not respond well to the rewetting methods. The clay content in Soil 3, 4, and 5 is generally lower than in the other soils. Interestingly, Soil 1, having the lowest clay content, responds positively to the rewetting method. This contrary phenomenon can be explained by the fact that there is no correlation to be found for clay and the rewettability of soil (Figure 14c). The samples Soils 1-7 exhibit clay contents ranging from approximately 11% to 27% . SoilX measurements of agricultural fields in Switzerland indicate a maximum clay content of 30.77% . As the observed

values fall within the expected range, clay content can be considered largely irrelevant for further investigations.

According to the expectations, the high sand content in Soil 1 should have led to a poorer rewetting effect than Soil 6. The key distinguishing factors between Soil 1 and Soil 6 are the Soil tillage method, SOC, clay, and sand content. Due to the insignificance of clay, these effects could hence be explained by SOC content and soil treatment.

Generally, soils with higher SOC tend to exhibit greater soil water repellency (SWR), which reduces their ability to absorb water and results in lower GWC at PWP. This effect largely depends on the type of organic compounds present and the specific surface area [46, 47]. This may explain why Soils 4, 5, and 6 demonstrate poor rewetting performance despite their lower SOC content (Figure 14b). Microbial activity influences the presence of hydrophobic compounds, as microbes can produce water-repellent substances [46]. Furthermore, a lower specific surface area due to the lower clay content can enhance SWR [47].

While enhanced SWR explains why sandy soils tend to be more water-repellent, it does not account for the large hysteresis effect observed. Dekker et al. (1998) found that SWR increases with rising temperature during the drying process. Their study shows that fine-textured soils only exhibit noticeable changes in SWR behaviour at higher temperatures ($>55^{\circ}\text{C}$). For sandy soils, this effect is already apparent at lower temperatures. This suggests that air-drying at 40°C causes a formation of organic carbon coatings and thereby enhancing their SWR as observed in Soils 4 and 5 [48].

As for Soil 6, the low rewetting capacity may occur due to soil treatment. In undisturbed soils, microbial populations are highest in the upper layers and decrease with depth [49]. This suggests that no-tillage practices promote microbial accumulation in soil [10]. This could explain why Soil 1 rewets more effectively than Soil 6 despite its textural properties suggesting otherwise. Due to no-tillage practice, Soil 6 may have developed greater SWR, causing the pronounced hysteresis effect.

4.8 Comparison of the Rewetting Methods

No rewetting method was able to rewet all soils within an insignificant range between RW and Fresh.

RW1 turned out to be an unsuitable rewetting option. The little amount of water added could be the main reason for why the method is unable to rewet the samples. The small amount of water likely leads to an irregular dispersion thereof, which means that the main drying curve on the hysteresis cannot be reached while drying.

RW2 appeared to be a slightly improved option, but overall does not yield satisfactory results., RW2 was unsuccessful in reaching the GWC at PWP of the Fresh samples with exception of Soil 2. The results suggest that Soil's 2 low sand and high silt contents could have led to the effective performance of RW2.

RW4 demonstrated the highest effectiveness of all tested methods. For the Soils 1, 2, and 3, it achieved a relative difference below 10% compared to the Fresh samples. Soil 3, with just over 10%, also yields an acceptable result. However, the method is not suitable for Soils 4, 5, and 6 having a low SOC content, indicating the need for further refinement, as they achieved a relative difference $>19\%$. It is particularly interesting that the supposedly less effective rewetting method

RW2 performs better for Soils 4, 5, and 6. It can be concluded that soil samples tend to respond positively to the RW4 rewetting method if they:

- have a low sand content (<50%),
- exhibit a relatively high silt content (>40%), and/or
- originate from tilled sites.

These characteristics appear to be the primary factors influencing rewetting performance. The results raise the question of which limitations prevented successful rewetting. A potential cause could be the insufficient equilibration time of one week. A longer equilibration time could be beneficial for sandy soils. In sandy soils with a low GWC at PWP, water is primarily distributed in the form of vapour, whereas in soils with higher clay content, a minimal water flow is still present [50].

Additionally, these soils may be more susceptible to air entrapment, which could inhibit rewetting by preventing water from fully saturating the sample. A possible solution could involve applying greater mechanical force to the sample by rubbing. In the current study, samples were only stirred with a needle and thus subjected to minimal mechanical force.

A potential approach for addressing these limitations and improving the method is proposed by Jørgensen and ten Damme (Denmark) [51]. In their approach, a specified amount of the soil sample is placed into a plastic bag, and a certain volume of tap water is added. The wetted soil samples stored in the bags are then compressed and rubbed to break up the aggregates. Subsequently, the sealed bags are stored in a refrigerator for at least two weeks to allow equilibration. For measurements, a portion of the sample can be taken from the bag and the water content can be calculated using the remaining material.

The effectiveness of this new Danish method for the various soil types would need to be tested using new samples. If this approach does not yield the desired improvement, using degassed water instead of tap water and a vacuum chamber could help refining the method, as both have proven impactful in RW4. Further parameters, such as land management practices, could also be examined in greater detail.

Apart from following the Danish approach proposed, using new sampled Fresh soil could provide further insights, as the Fresh and RW-treated samples were analysed by different persons, which could have led to inconsistencies. Furthermore, the close clustering of samples within the Soil Texture Triangle complicates identifying specific trends and distinguish between the different factors, thereby rendering an interpretation of the findings difficult. Finding a broader range of soil samples could be difficult, as most agricultural sites in Switzerland lie within this range. The further research could include the testing of samples dried at 105°C, even though the hysteresis effect is probably too distinctive.

5 Conclusion

This thesis set out to develop a standard method to rewet air-dried soil samples while considering the effects of hysteresis. It developed, tested, and evaluated four different rewetting methods using the WP4-T device. The findings show that rewetting methods and soil properties interact with each other, which determines the effectiveness of these methods.

The methods RW1, RW2, and RW4 used for the analysis exhibit varying effects on the outcome. RW1 turned out to be ineffective in rewetting soil. Similarly, RW2 is unsuitable except for Soil 2, which is characterised by a high silt content. In contrast, RW4 successfully facilitated the rewetting of Soils 1, 2, and 7, and led Soil 3 approaching the Fresh sample with an approximate deviation of -10% water content.

The evaluation of soil samples indicates that a low sand content ($<50\%$), a high silt content ($>40\%$), and samples obtained from tilled areas respond positively to the rewetting method RW4. Further analysis of additional samples with these characteristics could strengthen the findings.

For soils with a higher sand content, the tested methods do not yield successful results. This may be attributed to the physical properties of sand, including its low specific surface area and stronger tendency toward hydrophilic behaviour compared to silt and clay. At low water content, these properties significantly restrict water movement. In soils with a high sand content, equilibration predominantly occurs via the gas phase rather than through liquid water flow [50].

To further minimise the hysteresis effect, a prolonged equilibration period and the application of mechanical force to the sample may be beneficial. The newly proposed Danish method should be tested to assess its potential positive effects on sand-rich samples as well as on samples dried at 105°C . Furthermore, it should be examined whether this method also enhances the results for the samples that have successfully responded to the method RW4. Based on the findings of this study, collecting additional soils would require to record only sand and silt content, as well as land management practices.

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6 Appendix

6.1 Main Code

```
#####  
  
#Title: Test rewetting of air dried samples for WP4 measurementes  
  
#Year: 2024  
#Author: Matthias Lang  
  
#####  
  
#####  
### Initialize the Environment  
#####  
  
# old packages: , "lsr",,"nortest","rcompanion","dunn.test", "e1071"  
# Declare necessary packages  
pkgs_cran <- c("config", "tidyverse", "readxl", "FSA", "ggpubr", "  
  emmeans", "car", "afex", "dplyr","rcompanion","viridis","patchwork",  
  "ggpmisc")  
  
# Load packages  
source("01-LoadPkgs.R")  
  
# Read config  
source("02-ReadConfig.R")  
  
# Initialise  
source("03-Init.R")  
  
# Load functions  
source("04-LoadFunc.R")  
  
#####  
### Load sample info and WP4 data  
#####  
  
# Define sample info input file name and sheet  
filename_wp4_measurements <- "test_samples.xlsx"  
sheetname_sample_info <- "sample_information"  
sheetname_wp4_measurements <- "WP4_measurements"  
  
# Define WP4 data input file name and sheet  
filename_soilx <- "SoilX_Data_for_PPAvsWP4.xlsx"  
sheetname_soilx <- "WP4"  
  
# Load data  
source("05-LoadData.R")  
  
# Purge obsolete variables  
rm(sheetname_sample_info,filename_wp4_measurements, sheetname_wp4_  
  measurements, filename_soilx, sheetname_soilx, sample_info_soilx) #,  
  sample_info_WP4)
```

```

#####
### Wrangle data
#####

# SoilX data
data_soilx <- data_soilx_raw |>
pivot_longer(cols = c(starts_with("WP4_pF_"),starts_with("WP4_GWC_")),
  names_to = c(".value","sub_sample"), names_pattern = "(.*)_(.*)",
  values_to = c("pF","GWC")) |>
dplyr::rename("pF" = "WP4_pF", "GWC" = "WP4_GWC") |>
mutate(sub_sample = ifelse(sub_sample >= 1 & sub_sample <= 3, "A",
ifelse(sub_sample >= 4 & sub_sample <= 6, "B",
ifelse(sub_sample >= 7 & sub_sample <= 9, "C", sub_sample)))) |>
dplyr::mutate(treatment = as.factor(treatment), Core_No = as.factor(Core
_No), sub_sample = as.factor(sub_sample))

# WP4 data
data_WP4 <- data_WP4_raw |>
pivot_longer(cols = c(starts_with("pot"),starts_with("brutto")), names_
to = c(".value","sample_nr"), names_pattern = "(.*)_(.*)", values_to
= c("pot","brutto")) |>
dplyr::mutate(ID = as.factor(ID), treatment = as.factor(treatment), Core
_No = as.factor(NA), sub_sample = as.factor(sub_sample),
pF = log10(pot*10000),
GWC = ('brutto' - ('wet_tara' - 'dry_tara') - 'dry_brutto') / ('dry_brutto' - 'dry
_tara')) |>
dplyr::select(-sample_nr, -wet_tara, -dry_tara, -dry_brutto, -pot, -brutto)
|>
dplyr::select(all_of(colnames(data_soilx))) |>
dplyr::filter(!is.na(pF)) |>
filter(ID %in% paste0("Soil", 1:10))

# summarize and predict data F, HYPROP, RW1, RW2, RW3
data_total <- rbind(data_WP4, data_soilx) |>
group_by(ID, sub_sample, treatment, experiment, BD, SOC, clay, silt,
sand) |>
summarise(mean_GWC = mean(GWC),
GWC_4.2 = predict(lm(GWC ~ pF), newdata = data.frame(pF = 4.2)),
n=n()
)

# data wrangle for statistical analysis
data_stat <- filter(data_total, ID %in% c('Soil1', 'Soil2', 'Soil3', '
Soil4', 'Soil5', 'Soil6', 'Soil7')) |> #, 'Soil8', 'Soil9', 'Soil10')
) |>
rowid_to_column("Index")
summary(data_stat)

data_stat <- data_stat[-78, ] # adjusted data normality by neglecting
outliers
data_stat <- data_stat |> filter(treatment != "RW3")

#####
### statistical analysis
#####

```

```

# Normality testing visually and with Shapiro-Wilk test
nv <- lm(GWC_4.2 ~ ID * treatment, data = data_stat)
ggqqplot(residuals(nv))
#ggsave('plot_normal_distribution.jpg', width = 5, height = 5, dpi = 300
)

shapiro.test(residuals(nv))

# distribution of residuals by frequency
ggplot(data = data_stat, aes(x = resid(nv), color = factor(ID))) +
geom_histogram(bins = 30, fill = "grey", color = "black", alpha = 0.7) +
labs(title = "Distribution of Residuals by Frequency", x = "Residual [g/
g]", y = "Frequency") +
theme_minimal() +
scale_color_discrete(name = "ID")
#ggsave('plot_distribution_residuals.jpg', width = 5, height = 5, dpi =
300)

# Assumption of variance homogeneity between the groups using the Lavene
test
car::leveneTest(GWC_4.2~ ID*treatment, data = data_stat) # Pr(>F) ist >
0.05 daher Nullhypothese, Varianz zw. den beiden Gruppen ist homogen,
und somit gegeben

# interaction Plot
# Interaction Plot Treatment and GWC, tracer = ID
interplot_treatment(data_stat, "RW1")
interplot_treatment(data_stat, "RW2")
#interplot_treatment(data_stat, "RW3")
interplot_treatment(data_stat, "RW4")

# Interaction Plot ID and GWC, tracer = treatment
par(mfrow = c(2, 2), mar = c(4, 4, 2, 1))
interplot_ID(data_stat, "RW1", "(a)")
interplot_ID(data_stat, "RW2", "(b)")
#interplot_ID(data_stat, "RW3")
interplot_ID(data_stat, "RW4", "(c)")
par(mfrow = c(1, 1))
mtext("Soil Sample", side = 1, line = 3, cex = 1.0)
mtext(bquote("Mean GWC [g/g] at pF=4.2 [cm] ~ H[2]*0 ~ "), side = 2,
line = 3, cex = 1.0)

# Unbalanced Anova type III with afex
tw_aov <- aov_car(GWC_4.2~ ID*treatment + Error(Index), data = data_
stat, contrasts = list(ID = "contr.sum"))
summary(tw_aov$Anova) #Interactions are significant. Therefore a post-
hoc analysis is is necessary
afex::nice(tw_aov, es = "pes") # Effect size estimation

# Ranked Unbalanced ANOVA type III
data_stat$GWC_rank<- rank(data_stat$GWC_4.2)
tw_aov_rank <- aov_car(GWC_rank~ ID*treatment + Error(Index), data =
data_stat, contrasts = list(ID = "contr.sum"))
summary(tw_aov_rank$Anova) #Interactions are significant. Therefore a
post-hoc analysis is is necessary

# Post-hoc pair-wise comparison between 'Fresh' and all 'RWx' for each
treatment

```

```

post_hoc <- emmeans(tw_aov, pairwise ~ treatment | ID, adjust = "
  bonferroni")

#####
### Visualize data
#####

# Post-hoc-plot with comparison between 'Fresh' and 'RWx'
post_hoc_plot(data_stat, post_hoc)
#ggsave('boxplot_post_hoc_cleaned.jpg', width = 10, height = 8.5, dpi =
  300)

# plot measured GWC and pF of RW1-4
m1<-measurement_plot(data_WP4, "RW1", "pF", "GWC", "ID", "sub_sample", "
  (a)_")
m2<-measurement_plot(data_WP4, "RW2", "pF", "GWC", "ID", "sub_sample", "
  (b)_")
m3<-measurement_plot(data_WP4, "RW3", "pF", "GWC", "ID", "sub_sample", "
  (c)_")
m4<-measurement_plot(data_WP4, "RW4", "pF", "GWC", "ID", "sub_sample", "
  (d)_")
plot_measurement <- (m1 | m2) / (m3 | m4) +
plot_layout(guides = "collect") & theme(legend.position = "right")
rm(m1, m2, m3, m4)
print(plot_measurement)
#ggsave('plot_measurement_all_new.jpg', width = 16, height = 18, units=
  "cm", dpi = 300)

# Plotting effect of soil properties on GWC
# Plot GWC/pF depending on: (clay, sand, silt, SOC)
characteristic_plot(data_WP4, "sand", "[%]")
#ggsave('plot_characteristic_sand.jpg', width = 5, height = 5, dpi = 300
  )

# Plot GWC/pF depending on Bulk Density
characteristic_plot(data_WP4, "BD", "[g/cm3]")
#ggsave('plot_characteristic_BD.jpg', width = 5, height = 5, dpi = 300)

# Plot relative Difference depending on soil properties
relative_difference(data_stat)
#ggsave('plot_relativ_difference.jpg', width = 9, height = 6, dpi = 300)

# Plot meand difference depending on soil properties
mean_difference(data_stat)
#ggsave('plot_mean_difference.jpg', width = 9, height = 6, dpi = 300)

# Boxplot of all measurements
boxplot_sum(data_total, c("Fresh","RW1","RW2", "RW3","RW4"), "ID", "GWC_
  4.2", "treatment", c(0,0.3))
#ggsave('boxplot_comparison.jpg', width = 10, height = 7, dpi = 300)

#####
### save data
#####

## Save Output
#source("10-SaveOutput.R") <-- this file is not changed yet

```

6.2 Loading Template

```
# Load data
sample_info_soilx <- readxl::read_excel(path = paste0("./Input/",
  filename_soilx), sheet = sheetname_soilx)
sample_info_WP4 <- readxl::read_excel(path = paste0("./Input/",filename_
  wp4_measurements), sheet = sheetname_sample_info)

# Load WP4 sample measurements
data_WP4_raw <- readxl::read_excel(path = paste0("./Input/",filename_wp4
  _measurements), sheet = sheetname_wp4_measurements) |>
left_join(sample_info_WP4 %>% select(ID, sample, BD, SOC, clay, silt,
  sand), by = "ID")|>
dplyr::select(-'pot_4',-'brutto_4',-'pF1',-'GWC1',-'pF2',-'GWC2',-'pF3
  ',-'GWC3', -'pF4', -'GWC4',-'Comment')|>
select(ID,sample, everything()) |>
dplyr::filter(!is.na(pot_1)) |>
subset(ignore != "Yes") |>
dplyr::select(-ignore) |>
rename(experiment = sample) |>
mutate(treatment = ifelse(treatment == "VAC", "RW4", treatment),
  treatment = ifelse(treatment == "F", "Fresh", treatment),
  ID = factor(ID, labels = paste0("Soil", sort(unique(ID))))),
  experiment= sub("_.*", "", experiment))

# Load SoilX wet measurements
data_soilx_raw <- readxl::read_excel(path = paste0("./Input/",filename_
  soilx), sheet = sheetname_soilx) |>
dplyr::semi_join(sample_info_WP4, by = c("LTE_treat_block" = "sample", "
  depth"="depth")) |>
left_join(sample_info_WP4%>% select(ID, sample, depth, BD, SOC, clay,
  silt, sand), by = c("LTE_treat_block" = "sample", "depth"="depth"))
|>
dplyr::select(-LTE_treat_block, -replicate, -block, -depth, -plot_nr, -
  GWC_15000,- WP4_pF_10, -WP4_GWC_10) |>
select(ID, everything()) |>
mutate(treatment = "Fresh",
  ID = factor(ID, labels = paste0("Soil", sort(unique(ID)))))) |>
rename(experiment = LTE)
```

6.3 Functions

6.3.1 pivot_func

```
pivot_func <- function(data){
  data <- data|>
  pivot_longer(cols = c(starts_with("pot"),starts_with("brutto")), names_
    to = c(".value","sample_nr"), names_pattern = "(.*)_(.*)", values_to
    = c("pot","brutto")) |>
  dplyr::mutate(ID = as.factor(ID), treatment = as.factor(treatment), Core
    _No = as.factor(NA), sub_sample = as.factor(sub_sample),
  pF = log10(pot*10000),
  GWC = ('brutto'-( 'wet_tara'-'dry_tara' )-'dry_brutto')/('dry_brutto'-'dry
    _tara')) |>
  dplyr::select(-sample_nr,-wet_tara,-dry_tara,-dry_brutto,-pot,-brutto)
  |>
  dplyr::select(all_of(colnames(data_soilx))) |>
```

```
dplyr::filter(!is.na(pF))
}
```

6.3.2 interplot_treatment

```
# Interaction Plot
interplot_treatment <- function(data, RW){

data <- data |> filter(treatment %in% c("Fresh", RW))

data$ID <- ordered(data$ID)
data$treatment <- ordered(data$treatment)
levels_ID <- nlevels(data$ID)
nr_colors <- viridis(levels_ID, option = "plasma")

op <- par(mar = c(2,5,3,7), xpd = NA)
on.exit(par(op), add = TRUE)

with(data, {
ID <- ordered(ID)
treatment <- ordered(treatment)
interaction.plot(x.factor = data$treatment,
trace.factor = data$ID,
response = GWC_4.2,
#fixed = TRUE,
leg.bty = "o",
type = "l",
col = nr_colors,
lty = 1,
xlab = "",
ylab = "",
legend.title = NULL,
xpd = NA,
legend = FALSE
)
legend("topright",
legend = levels(data$ID),
col = nr_colors,
lty = 1,
cex = 0.9,
#y.intersp = 0.8,
#x.intersp = 0.4,
text.width = 0.16,
inset = c(-0.45, 0),
box.lty = 1
)
title(paste("Interaction Plot by Treatment: Fresh and", RW), cex.main =
1.1, ylab = bquote("Mean GWC [g/g] at pF = 4.2 [cm] ~ H[2]*0 ~ ")#
, xlab = "Treatment")
})
}
```

6.3.3 interplot_ID

```
# Interaction Plot
interplot_ID <- function(data, RW, subtitle){
```

```

data <- data |> filter(treatment %in% c("Fresh", RW))

data$ID <- ordered(data$ID)
data$treatment <- ordered(data$treatment)

with(data, {
#ID <- ordered(ID)
#treatment <- ordered(treatment)
interaction.plot(x.factor = data$ID,
trace.factor = data$treatment,
response = GWC_4.2,
fixed = TRUE,
#leg.bty = "o",
ylab = "",
xlab = "",
legend = FALSE,
)
#legend(6,1, leg.txt, pch = "sSvV", col = c(1, 3), cex = 1+(-1:2)/8)
legend("bottomright",
legend = c("Fresh",RW),
col = "black",
lty = c(2,1),
cex = 1,
y.intersp = 0.3,
x.intersp = 0.2,
text.width = 0.2,
seg.len = 0.5
)
#title(paste("Interaction Plot by Soil: Fresh and", RW), cex.main = 1.5)
mtext(paste(subtitle,"Fresh□and", RW), side = 1, line = 2.5, cex = 1.2,
adj = 0.5, family = "serif")
})
}

```

6.3.4 post_hoc_plot

```

post_hoc_plot <- function(data_stat, post_hoc){

#filtering results according to significance
filtered_results <- post_hoc$contrasts |>
as_tibble() |>
filter(str_detect(contrast, "Fresh") & str_detect(contrast, "RW")) |>
mutate(
Fresh = as.character(str_extract(contrast, "^\\w+")),
RWx = as.character(str_extract(contrast, "\\w+$")),
p.signif = case_when(
p.value < 0.001 ~ "***",
p.value < 0.01 ~ "**",
p.value < 0.05 ~ "*",
TRUE ~ "ns"
)
) |>
select(ID, Fresh, RWx, p.signif, p.value)
print(filtered_results)

```

```

# Boxplot for pairwise comparison Fresh and RW
ggplot(data_stat, aes(x = treatment, y = GWC_4.2, fill = treatment)) +
  geom_boxplot(outlier.shape = NA) +
  facet_wrap(~ ID, scales = "free_y") +
  stat_compare_means(
    comparisons = list(c("Fresh", "RW1"), c("Fresh", "RW2"), c("Fresh", "RW4"),
      c("Fresh", "RW3")), # , c("Fresh", "RW3")
    method = "t.test",
    p.adjust.method = "bonferroni",
    label = "p.signif",
    vjust = 0.5,
    tip.length = 0.01,
    bracket.size = 0.15
  ) +
  labs(title = "Comparison between Fresh and RW",
    x = "Treatment",
    y = bquote("Mean GWC [g/g] at pF = 4.2 [cm] ~ H[2]*0 ~ "),
    fill = "Treatment_Type") +
  scale_fill_grey(start = 0.3, end = 0.8) +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(
    axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1),
    strip.text = element_text(size = 12, face = "bold"),
    plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5),
    legend.position = "bottom",
    legend.text = element_text(size = 10),
    legend.key.size = unit(1.5, "lines"),
    legend.spacing.x = unit(0.5, 'cm'),
    strip.background = element_rect(fill = "grey85"),
    panel.background = element_rect(fill = "white")
  )
}

```

6.3.5 measurement_plot

```

# coloring legend
soil_colors <- c("Soil1" = "#440154", "Soil2" = "#482677", "Soil3" = "#3F4788",
  "Soil4" = "#31688E", "Soil5" = "#26828E", "Soil6" = "#1F9E89",
  "Soil7" = "#35B779", "Soil8" = "#6DCD59", "Soil9" = "#B8DE29",
  "Soil10" = "#FDE725")
soil_levels <- paste0("Soil", 1:10)

measurement_plot <- function(data, filter_value, x_var, y_var, color_var,
  shape_var, sub_title) {

  data <- data |> dplyr::filter(treatment %in% filter_value)

  data$ID <- factor(data$ID, levels = soil_levels)

  # set plot title and plot measured data
  plot_title <- paste("Measurements", paste(filter_value, collapse = "&"))

  ggplot(data,
    aes(x = pF, y = GWC,
    color = ID, shape = sub_sample)) +

```

```

geom_point() +
geom_line() +
scale_color_manual(values = soil_colors) +
theme_bw()+
theme(
  legend.position = "none",
  plot.caption = element_text(family = "serif", hjust = 0.5, size = 11)
) +
labs(caption = sub_title,
x = bquote(pF ~ "[cm" ~ H[2]*0 ~ "]"),
y = "GWC [g/g]",
color = "Soil_Type",
shape = "Sub_Sample",
axis.text=element_text(size=11)
)
}

```

6.3.6 Charact_plot

```

# plot for SOC, BD, clay, sand and silt depending on GWC and pF
charact_plot <- function(data, characteristic, SI){

plot_title <- paste("Effect of", characteristic, "on GWC and pF value")

ggplot(data |> filter(!ID %in% c("Soil8", "Soil9", "Soil10")),
aes(x = pF,
y = GWC,
shape = ID,
color = .data[[characteristic]])) +
geom_point( size = 3) +
scale_shape_manual(values = c(1:7)) +
scale_color_viridis_c() +
#scale_colour_gradient(low = "red", high = "blue") +
guides(
color = guide_colorbar(order = 1), # Sand color legend first
shape = guide_legend(order = 2) # Shape legend second
) +
labs(title = plot_title,
x = bquote(pF ~ "[cm" ~ H[2]*0 ~ "]"),
y = "GWC [g/g]",
color = paste(characteristic, SI)
) +
theme_bw()
}

```

6.3.7 relative_difference

```

plot_rel <- function(x_var, x_label, df_long) {
# plot relative difference
ggplot(df_long, aes_string(x = x_var, y = "rel_diff_Value", color = "RW"
)) +
geom_point(size = 1.5) +
geom_smooth(method = "lm", se = FALSE, linetype = "dashed") +
stat_poly_eq(use_label(c("R2", "p"))) +
scale_color_manual(values = c("RW1" = "#440154", "RW2" = "#31688E", "RW4"
" = "#6DCD59")) +

```

```

labs(x = x_label, y = "Relative_Difference_["%) +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none", aspect.ratio = 1)
}

```

6.3.8 relative_difference_plot

```

relative_difference <- function(data_stat){

medians <- data_stat |>
group_by(ID, treatment) |>
summarise(median_value = median(GWC_4.2, na.rm = TRUE)) |>
pivot_wider(names_from = treatment, values_from = median_value)|>
mutate(across(starts_with("RW"), ~ ((. - Fresh) / Fresh) * 100, .names =
  "rel_diff_{.col}"))
medians$clay <- c(10.96,22.53,11.61,14.89,19.13,27.23,22.05)
medians$BD <- c(1.47,1.45,1.54,1.57,1.52,1.43,1.31)
medians$SOC <- c(0.9,1.13,1.07,0.73,0.68,0.7,1.47)
medians$silt<- c(41.12,44.95, 29.74,24.92,23.79,36.03,37.33)
medians$sand <- c(47.92,32.52,58.66, 60.18,57.09,36.74,40.62)
print(medians)

df_long <- medians |>
pivot_longer(cols = starts_with("RW"),
names_to = "RW",
values_to = "Value") |>
pivot_longer(cols = starts_with("rel_diff_RW"),
names_to = "rel_diff_RW",
values_to = "rel_diff_Value") |>
filter(sub("rel_diff_", "", rel_diff_RW) == RW) |>
select(ID, RW, Value, rel_diff_Value, everything())
# print df_long
print(df_long)

# Plot relative Difference depending on soil properties
p1 <- plot_rel("BD", "(a)_Bulk_Density_[g/cm3]", df_long)
p2 <- plot_rel("SOC", "(b)_Soil_Organic_Carbon_["%]", df_long)
p3 <- plot_rel("clay", "(c)_Clay_["%]", df_long)
p4 <- plot_rel("sand", "(d)_Sand_["%]", df_long)
p5 <- plot_rel("silt", "(e)_Silt_["%]", df_long)

# extract legend out from the plots
legend_plot <- ggplot(df_long, aes(x = clay, y = rel_diff_Value, color =
RW)) +
geom_point(size = 3) +
scale_color_manual(values = c("RW1" = "#440154", "RW2" = "#31688E", "RW4"
" = "#6DCD59")) +
labs(color = "Rewetting_Method:") +
theme_minimal() +
theme(legend.position = "bottom")
legend <- get_legend(legend_plot)

# Put plots together with one legend
plot_rel_diff <- (p1 + p2 + p3) / (p4 + p5) / legend +
plot_layout(guides = "collect", heights = c(1, 1, 0.2))
print(plot_rel_diff)
}

```

6.3.9 mean_difference

```
mean_difference <- function(data_stat){
  mean_data <- data_stat |>
  group_by(ID, treatment) |>
  summarise(median_value = median(GWC_4.2, na.rm = TRUE)) |>
  pivot_wider(names_from = treatment, values_from = median_value)|>
  mutate(across(starts_with("RW"), ~ . - Fresh, .names = "mean_diff_{.col}"
  ))
  mean_data$clay <- c(10.96,22.53,11.61,14.89,19.13,27.23,22.05)
  mean_data$BD <- c(1.47,1.45,1.54,1.57,1.52,1.43,1.31)
  mean_data$SOC <- c(0.9,1.13,1.07,0.73,0.68,0.7,1.47)
  mean_data$silt<- c(41.12,44.95, 29.74,24.92,23.79,36.03,37.33)
  mean_data$sand <- c(47.92,32.52,58.66, 60.18,57.09,36.74,40.62)

  print(mean_data)

  df_mean <- mean_data |>
  pivot_longer(cols = starts_with("RW"),
  names_to = "RW",
  values_to = "Value") |>
  pivot_longer(cols = starts_with("mean_diff_RW"),
  names_to = "mean_diff_RW",
  values_to = "mean_diff_Value") |>
  filter(sub("mean_diff_", "", mean_diff_RW) == RW) |>
  select(ID, RW, Value, mean_diff_Value, everything())

  # Erstellen der einzelnen Plots
  p1 <- plot_mean("BD", "(a) Bulk Density [g/cm3]", df_mean)
  p2 <- plot_mean("SOC", "(b) Soil Organic Carbon [%]", df_mean)
  p3 <- plot_mean("clay", "(c) Clay [%]", df_mean)
  p4 <- plot_mean("sand", "(d) Sand [%]", df_mean)
  p5 <- plot_mean("silt", "(e) Silt [%]", df_mean)

  # Gemeinsame Legende aus einem separaten Plot extrahieren
  legend_plot <- ggplot(df_mean, aes(x = clay, y = mean_diff_Value, color
  = RW)) +
  geom_point(size = 3) +
  scale_color_manual(values = c("RW1" = "#440154", "RW2" = "#31688E", "RW4
  " = "#6DCD59")) +
  labs(color = "Rewetting Method")+
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.position = "bottom")

  legend <- get_legend(legend_plot) # Extrahiere die Legende
  # Alle Plots mit gemeinsamer Legende anordnen
  plot_mean_difference <- (p1 + p2 + p3) / (p4 + p5) / legend +
  plot_layout(guides = "collect", heights = c(1, 1, 0.2))

  # Plot anzeigen
  print(plot_mean_difference)
}
```

6.3.10 mean_difference_plot

```
plot_mean <- function(x_var, x_label, df_mean) {
```

```

ggplot(df_mean, aes_string(x = x_var, y = "mean_diff_Value", color = "RW
")) +
geom_point(size = 1.5) +
geom_smooth(method = "lm", se = FALSE, linetype = "dashed") +
stat_poly_eq(use_label(c("R2", "p")))) +
scale_color_manual(values = c("RW1" = "#440154", "RW2" = "#31688E", "RW4
" = "#6DCD59")) +
labs(x = x_label, y = "Mean_GWC_Difference[g/g]") +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none", aspect.ratio = 1)
}

```

6.3.11 Boxplot_data_sum

```

# Boxplot total_data_sum with F, RW1, HYPROP
boxplot_sum <- function(data, filter_value, x_var, y_var, colloring, y_
axis){

title_plot <- paste("Comparison of",
paste(filter_value, collapse = "&"))

ggplot(data |> dplyr::filter(treatment %in% filter_value),
aes(x = !!sym(x_var), y = !!sym(y_var), fill = !!sym(colloring))) +
geom_boxplot() +
ylim(y_axis) +
#xlim(!!sym(x_axis)) +
labs(title = title_plot,
x = x_var,
y = y_var,
fill = colloring) +
theme_minimal()
}

```


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